

DigiVet - Digitalisation of livestock data to improve veterinary public health

WP2 - Deliverable 2.4: Dashboards to support decision-making by relevant stakeholders within each case study.

This document signposts the software-based deliverables for each of the three case studies for deliverable 2.4. As for deliverable 2.3, we note that each of the deliverables is provided in the form of either code/scripts or full packages in the statistical programming language R; we chose this software due to it being open source, free of charge, active development over a 25+ year period, and strong uptake within the wider community of veterinary epidemiology and applied statistics (including within the project team). R can be obtained free of charge via the Comprehensive R Archive Network (CRAN): <https://cran.r-project.org>

We also note that active development of many of the tools shown here is expected to continue beyond the life span of the project; we therefore give installation instructions for both the static versions of the tools (created at the end of the project with fixed DOI) as well as the versions of the tools where development is expected to continue.

Case study 1

There are two tools provided for CS1 and deliverable 2.4: a user-friendly application for encrypting data using goldeneye (within the goldeneye package), and an interactive tool to help stakeholders understand the implications of adjusting the Danish national control programme for *Salmonella* Dublin (within the sdbuscontrol package). Each package can be installed in one of two ways; either via the repositories on GitHub (either the static DigiVet project repository or the development repository), or via the drat repository maintained by the Danish project partner. Instructions are given below.

Via drat (recommended)

Simply type the following to install the latest release versions of both goldeneye and sdbuscontrol:

```
install.packages(c("goldeneye", "sdbuscontrol"),
  repos=c("https://cran.rstudio.com/", "https://ku-awdc.github.io/drat/"))
```

Via GitHub

You will first need to install the remotes package in the usual way:

```
install.packages("remotes")
```

Then type the one of the following commands to either install goldeneye version 0.9.6-6 or sdbuscontrol version 0.3.0-2 from the DigiVet project's static repository, or the current version of goldeneye/sdbuscontrol from the active development repository:


```
remotes::install_github("digivet-consortium/goldeneye",
build_vignettes=TRUE)

remotes::install_github("digivet-consortium/sdubcontrol")

remotes::install_github("ku-awdc/goldeneye", build_vignettes=TRUE)

remotes::install_github("ku-awdc/sdubcontrol")
```

The static goldeneye repository is also stored on Zenodo with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10381612 (this is documented at <https://github.com/digivet-consortium/goldeneye>). The static sdubcontrol repository is also stored on Zenodo with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.10378407 (this is documented at <https://github.com/digivet-consortium/sdubcontrol>).

Launching the applications

To launch the applications, run one of the following from within R:

```
goldeneye::run_app()

sdubcontrol::app_launch()
```

Full usage instructions are given on screen. Full package documentation for both goldeneye and sdubcontrol are also provided as an appendix to this deliverable.

Case study 2

Recent EU legislation (article 57 of Regulation 2019/6) implies that the member states are mandated to report AMU to the EU starting in 2024. Through the work in WP1 and a workshop in WP3 with relevant stakeholders from 5 different countries, we learned how the current landscape and system for calculating AMU varies, depending on how antimicrobials are sold and used, the legislation, and available data sources in each country. Therefore, in D2.2, we focused on formulating a common data structure that can be derived from existing data sources in each country. This structure then can serve as a foundation for analysis and visualization using a universally adaptable tool. As an example of such tool, we developed AMView (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400887>), an R shiny application that visualizes AMU data in animals. Once data is formatted into the common data structure, AMView visualizes the data both in ‘Maps’ and ‘Trends’ with various filtering and grouping options (sva-epi.shinyapps.io/AMView/). The AMView package also includes a feature to generate artificial data based on the user’s needs in case one wants to explore the tool without real data. The documentation on how to use the tool has been described with the package ([GitHub - digivet-consortium/AMView: Shiny application to visualize antimicrobial use data](#)). To increase the usability of AMView, an example of how a real-world data can be fit into the common data structure has been described with the AMU data from Norway (D2.3) with the R code (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10400887>). Further improvements on the tool are planned to incorporate the feedback from the workshop with key stakeholders in WP3 (D3.1).

Case study 3

Commercial pig movements are an important factor in the spread of African swine fever (ASF). The analysis of these movements can provide valuable intelligence for preparedness and outbreak response. For example, network analysis can determine a movement network's effectiveness at transmitting infection, and the relative importance of different holdings and connections therein. Additionally, incorporating detailed movement data into disease transmission models can improve the accuracy of predictions of these models, such as final outbreak size, and the speed at which this is reached. The effective use of pig movement data for these purposes is, however, complicated by a variety of challenges, including issues relating to data, and requirements for specific analytic expertise.

The aim of WP2 for CS3 is to address these challenges by developing a toolkit that facilitates the dataflow from pig movement data to network analysis and to transmission models of ASF, and that helps users with interpreting the outputs from these analyses. This toolkit comes in the form of an open-source R package, *movenet* (<https://digivet-consortium.github.io/movenet/>), and an accompanying interactive app to cater to users who prefer a graphical user interface. These tools are being developed through all tasks in WP2.

In Task 2.2, we focused on addressing data-related issues: we developed a flexible data parsing functionality that converts datasets to a common data structure, and a privacy-enhancing workflow. In Task 2.3, we developed the main analytic workflows of the package: a network analysis workflow producing a standardised, downloadable report with tables and graphs displaying network metrics of relevance to disease spread; and a modelling workflow that converts movement and holding data into a transmission matrix, which then serves as input for a *SimInf* transmission model.

In this task, we developed a *shiny* app with a graphical user interface to the *movenet* toolkit, to extend the reach of the toolkit to people who do not normally use R. The app allows users to upload data, generate networks and visualise analyses in an interactive manner. Interpretive text is also provided, to support decision-making and to facilitate uptake by users with limited network analysis expertise.

We chose to make the *movenet* app a downloadable software instead of an online dashboard, as privacy concerns inhibit the public display of movement data, and even the uploading of these data to a restricted-access web app hosted on a remote server may be problematic. The app is open-source software, and will continue to be developed; the version released with this Deliverable can be downloaded from Zenodo (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10284041>), and any latest version from GitHub (<https://github.com/digivet-consortium/movenetapp>). The software includes a README file with installation instructions and two use case scenarios; further documentation regarding the underlying functionalities is available within the *movenet* package (see Deliverable 2.3) and on its web page (<https://digivet-consortium.github.io/movenet/>).